

Characterization of regional binding of clinical amyloid tracers in autosomal dominant and sporadic Alzheimer's disease brains and their interactions with resveratrol

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Introduction

PET imaging using amyloid tracers showed different regional binding pattern in autosomal dominant Alzheimer's disease (ADAD) with atypical forms of amyloid plaques compared to sporadic Alzheimer's disease (sAD). We test the hypothesis that detection of brain A β pathology by amyloid tracer depends on conformation of brain A β aggregates as well as on amyloid tracer structure.

Methods

Cortical and subcortical tissues from 6 ADAD (58 \pm 11 y) with APP^{swe}, PS1 M146V², PS1 E49 mutation³, 13 sAD (69 \pm 9 y) and 14 control cases (74 \pm 12 y) were analyzed with saturation, competitive binding assays and autoradiography (using ³H-PIB, ³H-florbetaben, ³H-AZD2184 and Methyl-³H-BTA-1) as well as Bielschowsky silver staining.

Results

Comparison of binding properties of different amyloid tracers in the frontal cortex and striatum of sAD and ADAD.

³H-PIB, ³H-florbetaben, ³H-AZD2184 and BTA-1 showed a shared high-affinity binding site (0.1-1.0 nM) and a low-affinity binding site with varying affinity (7-325 nM) in the frontal cortex of sAD.

AZD2184 detected in contrast to PIB and BTA-1 and a third binding site (33 nM) in the frontal cortex of ADAD.

Fig 1. ³H-PIB competition assays with BTA-1 and AZD2184 on the frontal cortex and striatum of sAD and ADAD.

Different regional amyloid tracer binding in ADAD and sAD brain

Significantly increased binding of ³H-PIB and ³H-AZD2184 were measured in the striatum of ADAD compared to sAD and control cases, with divergent ³H-PIB and ³H-AZD2184 binding pattern.

Fig 2 Regional difference in ³H-PIB and ³H-AZD2184 binding in ADAD and sAD frontal cortex and striatum homogenates. * p < 0.05, ** p < 0.01, *** p < 0.001.

Amyloid tracers binding influenced differently by resveratrol

Resveratrol reduced the binding of various amyloid tracers in the frontal cortex slide and homogenate from sAD to different degrees, with largest effect observed in ³H-AZD2184 binding.

Fig 3 ³H-AZD2184, ³H-PIB, ³H-florbetaben and Methyl-³H-BTA-1 autoradiogram in the presence of 100 μ M resveratrol in sAD frontal cortex slides.

Phenol interactions with amyloid tracer binding depend on tracer structure

Resveratrol and p-nitrophenol, but not β -naphthal largely reduced the binding of ³H-AZD2184 in sAD frontal cortex homogenates, suggesting a structure dependent interaction.

Fig 4 Effect of resveratrol (Res), p-nitrophenol (PNP) and β -naphthal (β N) on amyloid tracer binding in sAD frontal cortex. * p < 0.05, *** p < 0.001.

Conclusions

- ADAD differ from sAD cases in the AZD2184 detected an additional binding sites in the frontal cortex as well as an increased binding in the striatum of ADAD compared to sAD, as possible sign for differences in A β plaque composition.

- Differences in the binding properties and interactions with resveratrol between amyloid tracers imply binding to different sites on A β fibrils or to different A β structures.

References

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